

TEACHING OF ARTS IN EDUCATION: TRAINING AND PROFESSIONAL TEACHING

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Grosso), Cuiabá city, Brazil..**E-mail:** gustavocaraujo@yahoo.com.br**Article Type:****Review****Keywords:***Teaching in Arts. Teacher
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The manuscript aims to discuss the teaching of Arts in education, through theoretical research in line with the experience while teaching this discipline held in Uberlândia, State of Minas Gerais, Brazil. The informations obtained in situ were qualitatively analyzed in the light of the theories underlying this study. Theories pointed this work one teaching in Arts in the history of Brazilian education, implication in issues of teacher precarious, based on the lack of sufficient resources for the continuing education of professionals and related problems versatility, placing the discipline of Art as "knowing subsidiary" in relation to other subjects of the school curriculum. Experiences in basic education unveiled the evaluation of Arts and Reading images, these are issues that need to be based on the objectives and contents proposed activities and projects to be carried out with the students and the school. Problematizing them in teacher training courses is of paramount importance for the development of a good work Arts teacher. From this perspective, this work cast the training and professionalization, to contribute to the educational debate on the issue at hand, intending to produce and socialize knowledge resulting in the interpretative process, reflective and constructive present in qualitative research in education.

INTRODUCTION

This research embodies the interest in discussing the teaching of Arts in education, through theoretical research in line with the experience of the discipline while teaching the state and municipal city of Uberlândia, State of Minas Gerais. The information obtained in situ were qualitatively analyzed in the light of the theories underlying this study. From this perspective, attempts to analyze the teaching of Arts in the history of Brazilian education relating it to the training and professionalization today.

It was assumed that educational research arises from experienced and pedagogical practices produced in the educational context. Thus, I believe that research with an emphasis on teaching and teacher professionalization is characterized by questions and reflections produced over the practices and knowledge of teachers.

To make this discussion, I use the aid of theoretical (BARBOSA, 1988, 1991; CALADO, 1994; GATTI and BARRETO, 2009; IAVELBERG, 2012, 2003; LELIS, 2004; NÓVOA, 2012, 2008, 1998, 1992; OSINSKI, PENIN, 2009; 2001; SAVIANI, 2009; SOUSA, 2006; TARDIF, 2002; TINOCO, 2010) in the building reflections in this manuscript.

This work has reference in qualitative research interpretive (BOGDAN and BIKLEN, 1999) in an attempt to produce reflections on the theme discussed, since "as educational researchers have the challenge of integrating theories and create new knowledge without,

however, exhausting their interpretive possibilities" (SOUSA, 2006, p. 70).

The text is divided into three levels of analysis, namely: first, seek to present a brief historical discussion on the formation of arts in teaching in education, begun in the 1940s, through theoretical data, which brought notes to understand How has teaching drawing at Arts in the history of Brazilian education.

Then expound some discussions about the training and professionalization, with reflections of important authors of educational literature to problematize the teaching in Arts in Brazilian education.

In the third part, It was proposed to discuss some experiences in basic education in the city of Uberlândia, Minas Gerais, as a teacher of Arts, of which emphasize the assessment of Arts and working with the reading of images as relevant and "challenging" pedagogical practices of the teacher of this area being examined to the theoretical frameworks that underpin this work.

Finally, some considerations about the reflections constructed in this manuscript were presented, related to teaching and training in Arts and professionalization, however, without exhausting the possibilities of new interpretations and discussions on the theme emphasized in this study.

In discussing the training and professionalization of Arts, this work aims to contribute to the educational debate on the issue at hand, in which they intend to

produce and socialize knowledge resulting in the interpretive process, reflective and constructive present in qualitative research in education.

TEACHING IN ARTS EDUCATION IN THE HISTORY OF BRAZILIAN

History of Arts subject in Brazilian education that informs teaching in Arts began to be drafted from the 1940s, through studies of the English philosopher Herbert Read and the American philosopher Viktor Lowenfeld, who investigated the aesthetic education and art as object of knowledge, and the development of creative capacity of individuals and aesthetics, respectively (OSINSKI, 2001).

Around the same time came to Brazil in "Little School of Art" created by educator Augusto Rodrigues, who proposed a school of art founded on the expression and creative freedom, advocated earlier by Herbert Read (SOUSA, 2006 and LELIS, 2004). In this perspective, it seems that this type of teaching art has influenced the practice of theoretical and methodological Arts teacher, and propose a renewal in the educational context of this teaching in Brazilian schools.

After being enacted Law no. 4,024 in 1961, reshaping the basic education in the country, created a department of Art and Education at the University of Brasilia, federalized this time, with the intention to better prepare teachers in this area during their educational practices and produce research on Art and Education (LELIS, 2004).

Therefore, with the creation of the Law n. 5.692/71, also aiming to reshape education in Brazil, is finally the requirement in Art Education in schools, called "Arts Education", much discussed since the '20s (LELIS, 2004), however, still considered "activity" and not discipline in education.

In the 1980s emerged organizations and meetings between teachers of Arts (SOUSA, 2006; LELIS, 2004), with proposed changes and renovations in Art Education at school so problematic over the years in the educational sphere, which originated Brazil, subsequently, movement called "Arts Education." Some years later, in 1996, promulgated the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education no. 9394 that, in addition to reformulate the Brazilian basic education, in its article 26, put the teaching of art in schools as a mandatory component of basic education and, according to Sousa (2006), was the closing time of the discussions around the compulsory education Art in schools. With this information, one can state that it is from this moment that discussions on theoretical, methodological and conceptual start to permeate teaching in Art in Brazilian pedagogical thought.

With the teaching of art, and no more "Arts Education" as required in basic education, resulting in new and more training courses for teachers of Arts, proposed a renewal theory and method of this teaching, but guided mostly in experiences and contributions of the methodology called Triangular Proposal, the teacher and

researcher in Art/Education Ana Mae Barbosa, consolidating as main proposal aimed at improving the quality of education offered in schools of art and Brazilian so he could meet effectively the real needs of students in learning and art meet.

This new conception of art education that occurred during the 1990s has made this area of knowledge obtained its recognition and significance effectively as a compulsory subject in the curriculum of schools in Brazil with the creation of the National Curriculum 1997 and 1998, also known as PCN's by the Ministry of Education.

It is noteworthy that educational reforms in recent years in Brazil, aimed at democratization and universalization of education, as the Laws of Guidelines and Bases of Education and the National Curriculum have revealed attempts to improve the quality of education and teaching practice teaching not being different in art education, seeking to rethink the role of the teacher in the school, recognizing that it is necessary and proposed significant changes to quality education.

TRAINING AND PROFESSIONAL TEACHING

Historically speaking, the issue of teacher preparation in Brazil starts for the first time in 1827, with the Law Schools of the First Letters, when teachers were required to be educated in the mutual teaching method for teaching and subsequently extended the Normal Schools (SAVIANI, 2009).

However, the first training courses for teachers in Brazil were created in the late 19th century, called Normal Schools, which formed the teachers to work in secondary level or the "first letters" (GATTI and BARRETO, 2009). With regard to the effectiveness of teacher professionalization in Brazil, the same occurred with the creation of the University of São Paulo in 1931, with the emergence of teacher training courses for primary school, high school level. Six decades later, with the creation of the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education no. 9394 1996 was proposed training in higher education (PENIN, 2009).

By emphasizing this professionalism, attention to the knowledge and expertise of the teacher seem to be relevant in their teaching, to understand that both relate to the process of professionalization throughout his career, and need to be rethought, evaluated and questioned ever, especially in the educational context, the place where your practice develops effectively.

Tardif (2002), in their studies to address the knowledge of teachers, their training and profession for their teaching practices, says knowing manifest not only individually, but also collectively, the relationship between teachers and students in the school. In light of the thought of the same author, not only the continuing education courses, but the schools are important areas for training and professional development, ongoing research and production of new knowledge and techniques.

In the wake of thought Nóvoa (1998), such changes should cover the historicity of the teaching profession and responsibilities are not only the state but also of school education, to provide a space for intense and continuous collective process of contextualization and teacher training. Given this exposure, it is important to note that: not easy to define professional knowledge: it has a theoretical dimension, but it is not just theoretical; has an empirical dimension, but not unanimously produced by experience. We are facing a set of knowledge, skills and attitudes, more (and this is more important) its mobilization in a particular educational activity (NÓVOA, 2008, p. 231).

In addition to understanding the professionalization as a process of formation of a guy in a profession (PENIN, 2009), it is important to note that the changes in the educational field are constructed from changes in their practices of teachers and schools "welcome" these subjects.

Faced with reflections on teaching in Art and professionalization, it is important to reflect the school as an area of knowledge production. It is the field in which the teacher will organize, analyze, plan and reflect on their practice and profession in education, noting that "teachers must be trained, not only for a teaching relationship with students, but also to a social relationship with the 'local communities'" (NÓVOA, 2008, p. 229).

ARTS IN TEACHING: TALES OF A TEACHER

Through the scientific literature on teaching and art education, and experience as a teacher of basic education it is possible to see in this new millennium teaching of art bringing new proposals for free expression and creation processes, instilling new and relevant research focusing on teacher training, which brings notes relevant to the construction of reflections in this work.

By directing our gaze to the experience in basic education, some issues were reviewed that are relevant to understand the teacher's work, in this case, specific Arts teacher, namely the evaluation of Arts which, according to the reflection built the light of the thought of Tinoco (2010, p. 14):

is subject little studied, both for historical reasons as the very specification of the knowledge area, the assessment in Visual Arts is a land of many controversies. The breadth of knowledge and concepts that comprise the Visual Arts, the constant conceptual modifications, as well as the organization of their systems reinforce the difficulty of assessment in Art, Art review, because it is no longer easy. The social, political and market involving art criticism, for example, with their constant cases of repudiation or overvaluation of the new, the unusual and creative, give the dimension of the problem.

On this assessment, I have noticed many teachers

having difficulty in assessing Arts because unlike the other subjects of the school curriculum, such an evaluation, which can be a note or concept, is related, in most cases, the processes, and not to products, evaluating over the creative process during the development of the art work - making art, not just the final result.

Thus, suppose that the "complexity" of evaluating in Arts may be due to the diversity of existing different art materials such as pencils, brushes, papers, and other media among different artistic productions made/created by students in the Arts classes, which require a "look" in aesthetic knowledge by the teacher.

Another issue that was share in this work refers to the reading of images in the classroom, in which understanding the relevance of studies on visual literacy, for images/works/artwork produced in the school can be better understood and used adequately for the teacher to work with images in the educational process. When talking about literacy, I mean the ability to understand and express themselves through a written or visual representation (CALADO, 1994).

The question of the importance of reading imagery comes primarily at a time when its dissemination occurs increasingly intense and fast, due to technological means of information, communication and the emergence of new creative processes, such as computer art, in entering the "world of images", which in fact brings to mind the need to become literate and visually, which is no different in teaching Arts, having the image of its main objects of study.

Images are polysemic, ambiguous, provoke different emotions that make us see and know cranking repertoires, often appear to linked words (texts). Therefore, establishing pedagogical questions to think about the pedagogy of the images in the school culture is a priority as the teacher know how to use images (LAMPERT, 2009, p. 156), it must be considered, because these reflects as Professors of Art during their practice, must articulate theory and practice in creative processes, so that the classes have quality and fulfill their role in the school curriculum (IAVELBERG, 2012). For this, I believe that the experiences and experiments in art of teaching are critical to a successful development of work with students.

Art is a form of expression and knowledge. His teaching aims to ensure students access to the cultural and historical heritage and enabling acts of creation and knowledge in different languages of art. Doing and knowing art school the student will be recognized as competent reader of the works of artists and to enhance the role of art in society and in the lives of individuals (IAVELBERG, 2012, p. 06).

In dialogue with Bosco (2011) agree that the teaching of contemporary art has shown the importance of reading a work of art and interpret it, but not purely formal, anyway, understanding the work of art as a conglomeration of colors and shapes but in a way in which it seeks growth and aesthetic knowledge,

producing new meanings and, consequently, new interpretations of reality, leading the individual to acquire a good understanding of artistic production.

However, another issue that I encounter on the path while teaching in Arts refers to the versatility. In practice pedagogical Arts teacher can often come across with other teachers teaching arts without even having specific training for this discipline, which in fact, can bring problems for the training of the student, for example, the teacher who has training in arts teaching content or subject matter that their students so misguided.

On this subject, the author Magalhães (2002) contributes saying the versatility of Arts in teaching motivated several debates and discussions of teachers in this area who sought, through meetings and meetings between teachers, solutions to the existing problem in their training as teachers and the educational context in which it was this discipline: considered a knowing and secluded alternative school curriculum.

The versatility - smattering of all artistic languages - as evidenced methodological approach in teaching and learning in Art, revealed ineffective for general training that did not match / matches the professional to be formed, empowered to meet the diverse realities of Brazilian cultural contexts and to contemporary trends arising from the technological age. Clearly this methodological proposal left serious gaps in teacher education and educational practices in art, which contributed to the shallowness of the area in school curricula and prevented systematized knowledge, historical context and specificity of each language arts (Magalhães, 2002 pp. 162-163).

In this perspective the authors Gatti and Barreto (2009) makes an important observation: versatility has historical remnants from the 1930s, a decade before the faculty of Arts to be outlined in Brazilian education, when, to meet the demand for teachers in schools of that time, the government added a year with disciplines in training bachelors degree, with the intent to train teachers for secondary education.

Regarding the formation of the Arts teacher, the locus of research, in this case, in the city of Uberlândia, Minas Gerais, one can find courses for continuing education offered by state and local departments of education, and scientific events as "Encounter and Reflections in Art Education," sponsored by the Institute of Arts of the Federal University of Uberlândia, the University Museum of Art - Muna and the City Hall of that city and the Continuing Education Programme for Basic Education Teachers, offered annually by the Dean of Extension, Federal University of Uberlândia - PROEX / UFU, attending public school teachers and state schools.

Concerning this teacher training, state of Minas Gerais offers Teacher Training Program, created by the state Department of Education, in partnership with the regional offices of education, municipalities and universities, as an example of a program for training continued to basic education teachers.

In this sense, I could see in some teacher education

courses in Uberlândia, both sponsored by the Federal University of Uberlândia, as the State and Municipal Education, few studies focused on the evaluation of Arts and Reading images therefore due to be two issues "challenging" for the teaching of this discipline, I could see the second experiment with this discipline in education, it is important that such courses could discuss these works, in order to better prepare teachers in their teaching.

However, it is widely available at a few classes in Brazilian schools and considering the experience of teaching in arts education, it is clear that arts education contributes materially to the training, knowledge, and artistic and aesthetic development of the students, "making it those able to insert itself in reality critically and creatively" (DAL'MASO, 2011, p. 56).

Given these considerations, it is important to understand art as language, cultural and artistic manifestation, essential in the formation of the human being, since the history of mankind informs through cave paintings art to be the first form of communication and expression of human society.

FINAL THOUGHTS

I have observed in the educational sphere that teaching in Arts comprises processes and practices of production, organization, socialization and appropriation of knowledge and expertise that develop in educational spaces, related to social and historical context in which it was built.

The theories used in this study explore one teaching in Arts in the history of Brazilian education issues involved in teacher training precarious, based on the lack of sufficient resources for the ongoing training of these professionals, and problems related to versatility, which is even present in today.

With regard to the importance given to this subject in the school curriculum, we understand that it is considered "alternative knowledge", as mere complimentary activity (IAVELBERG, 2003), which in fact, is a subject that needs be thoroughly debated in the core education, emphasizing its importance and the contributions they can bring to the full formation of the student.

In reflections on training and professionalization, it was established that the area teaching not only involves a process of organization, planning, observation, analysis and reflection by the teacher in the context of their practice, but also requires appropriate conditions offered by the school the work of teachers, especially in the Arts classes, which usually has little room to work with students artistic materials and procedures, and training courses aimed at teaching this, which in fact implies a constant investigation of research about the profession and its teacher-education practices.

With regard to experiences in education, these unveiled for this study that the assessment arts and

reading pictures are issues that need to be based on the objectives and contents proposed activities and projects to be carried out with the students and the school. Problematicize them in teacher training courses is of paramount importance for the development of a good work Arts teacher.

In addition, it is necessary to point out the importance of understanding the teacher as a social-historical subject, which measured the knowledge and knowledge to their students.

I finish this job, but not the educational debate provoked by him, noting that the reasoning developed in this research may lead to new interpretations and reflections aimed at teaching Arts and professionalization in the core education, contributing to the educational debate and further studies may discuss this topic in order to contribute to a quality education is vital to the development of a nation.

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